

INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOUR OF STUDENTS OF SHRI KUMARESHWAR B.ED COLLEGE, HANGAL HAVERI (KARNATAKA) : A CASE STUDY

Shri Manjunath M.Ningoji

Librarian, Shri Kumareshwar College of Education,
Hangal-581104 Dt: Haveri, Karnataka, India

Kavya V.

B.Sc, B.Ed., Shri Kumareshwar College of Education,
Hangal-581104 Dt: Haveri, Karnataka, India

ABSTRACT

Academic library play a pivotal role in providing valuable services to the users. This study was designed to investigate to find out the knowledge and awareness of information literacy among the information of seeking behaviour 120 B.Ed student from Shri Kumareshwar College of Education in Hangal. In this study will identify the current information seeking behaviours of student teachers are described & discussed from information seeking from information channels level of satisfaction & the students behaviors i.e., attitude the students execute while seeking information the results revealed that majority of teacher educators believed that there information seeking help them in attaining continuing professional development

Key words: Information Seeking Behavior B.Ed Students, Information Literacy, Libraries, Education.

Cite this Article: Shri Manjunath M.Ningoji and Kavya V, Information Seeking Behaviour of Students of Shri Kumareshwar B.Ed College, Hangal Haveri (Karnataka) : A Case Study, *International Journal of Library & Information Science*, 10(1), 2021, pp. 6-11. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12618625>

<http://www.iaeme.com/IJLIS/issues.asp?JType=IJLIS&VType=10&IType=1>

1. INTRODUCTION

According to Samuel Johnson : Knowledge is of two kinds we know a subject ourselves or we know where we can find information on it” Wilson(2000) defines purposive seeking for information as a consequence of a need to satisfy some goal. In the course of seeking the

individual may interact with manual information system i.e., newspaper, computer-based system www information-seeking behavior considered as a vital area in recent research in library & information science. Fulfilling the library user's information needs is the major task of librarians in education institutions starting from school to university education. According to Bruce(2005) : "Information plays a significant role in our daily professional & personal lives and we are constantly challenged to take charges of the information that we need for work. Fun and everyday decisions and task "

Recent literatures on information seeking behavior reveal that students help them in updating their knowledge, refining their attitude developing skills & performing better practices to excel in their education. Information seeking behavior among B.Ed students is the need of the hour since the programme has been revised from 1 year to 2 years and the students should clear CTET/STET its compulsory for getting jobs after the course this present study investigates information – seeking behavior among the students of Shri Kumareshwar college of Education, Hangal, District Haveri (Karnataka)

2. OBJECTIVES & BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

- Teachers play key role in the information age. They are the role models of future students. student teachers information seeking help them in their teaching – learning process
- They should empower themselves on current teaching methods, knowledge, attitude, teaching learning process, through lifelong learning practices.
- Information seeking behavior empowers student teachers for their overall development during the course and after the course of B.Ed

3. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The scope of the research project "Information Seeking Behaviour of the students of Shri Kumareshwar college of Education, Hangal, District Haveri A Case Study " lies for the period of 2019-20 An attempt is made to know how far the library has helped in fulfilling the demands or requirements of student teachers.

4. METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out by survey method based on questionnaire which has been distributed among the all B.Ed both in 1st and IInd years. Students of the College. In total 150 questionnaires were distributed out of which to the 120 students consisted of the items on profile characteristics, information seeking behaviour and beliefs of students on information seeking behaviour.

5. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study will identify the information need, information seeking process information channels level of satisfaction and the students behaviour viz, attitude the students execute while seeking information. Further the study also extend to identify the services offered at the library & student teacher opinion on library staff.

5.1. About the Library

Shri Kumareshwar B.Ed College library having in all respect very good physical infrastructure facilities our staff& students. It has rich collection of books e-resources services & reference, information services, e-resources and fully digitalized facility to the users. The library provided internet, wifi,e-library, e-books, e-Grantalaya, N-IIST(INFLIBNET) Bar-Coad system on Issuing books etc., and spacious separate girls , boys and faculty for reading facility. The

cognitive skills are developed by making the innovative information seeking behaviours services. In terms of overall library facilities services majority of students teachers respondents are satisfied above library staff & they will get the maximum benefit.

Library with collection of 12842 text books, reference books (Encyclopedia, Dictionaries year books etc.) 400 charts & maps, 12 Journals (NCERT) 10 news paper etc. Old question paper etc. In librarian conducted every year 2 to 5 times orientation programmes & TET/CTET, job competitive examination test on behalf of students teacher feature job purpose.

Library ‘Vision’

“ It provides welcoming environment for student teachers and staff engaged in teaching learning process”

Library ‘Mission’

“ To create new knowledge to increace understanding and developed wisdom”

Library ‘Motto’

“Right information to the right users , right book at right time users satisfaction through quality information service.

6. DATA ANALYSIS & RESULTS

The data for the research study was collected through questionnaires percentage method is used to derive finding of the study. Shri Kumareswar College of Education, Hangal District Haveri (Karnataka) has two years B.Ed programme. For this study 120 students were selected from both the year of study with regard to the distribution of respondents by sex all of them were male & female.

Table 1 Frequency of Library Visit

Duration	Students	Percentage
Daily	48	40.00%
Weekly	23	19.17%
2/3 times in a week	37	30.83%
Monthly	12	10.00%
Total	120	100%

Above table shown majority of students 40% are visiting the library on daily basis which is followed by 2-3 time in a week by 30.83% , 19.17% visit library on weekly basis while 10% student comes in the library monthly. This shows that most of the student’s teacher are visiting the library & know the importance of the library.

Table-2 Time Spent in Library

Time spent	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 30 Minutes	44	36.67%
Half hours to one hours	48	40.00%
1 Hours to 2 hours	22	18.33%
More than 2 Hours	6	05.00%
Total	120	100%

This table shows that the most of students spend in the library by students is 30 minutes to one hours (36.67%) This table shows that student is spending time in library for their academic needs.

Table 3 Students Information Seeking Behaviour through Library

Do you update KAP for the course through information seeking behaviour	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	120	100
No	0	0
Total	120	100%

With regards the student's information seeking behavior all the B.Ed student teachers respondent that 100% they update knowledge attitude and practices (KAP) through information seeking behaviour. This table shows that helped them to update their knowledge, attitude and practices.

Table 4 Students Information Seeking Practices

The way updating your learning for knowledge, attitude skills through library	Frequency	Percentage
Reading books	77	64.17%
Reading Journals, Magazines	16	13.33%
Reading news papers, clipping service	27	22.50%
Total	120	100%

Table 4 shows that information seeking practice is self-directed, motivated from within in most of the time with focusing frequency of updating (KAS) for the programme, most of the students 77(64.17%) opined that through reading books they update their KAS and 27(22.50%) students opined that they update their KAP through reading newspaper clippings and 16(13.33%) students responded that they update their KAS through reading Journals & Magazines.

Table-5 Students Information Seeking Practices Apart from Library

The mot way of updating your learning for KAS through other modes	Frequency	Percentage
Pursuing Distance/Open/Online Course	14	11.66%
Attending Training Porgrammes	79	65.83%
Participating in workshop/seminar/PPT	27	22.50%
Total	120	100%

Table 5 shows in response updating knowledge attitude & skills (KAS) through after modes more no. of students 65.83% opined attending training programmes were there mode of information seeking related in their leatting 22.50% of students opined that participating in workshop/Seminar/PPT etc is their modes of information seeking. Minimum no of students 11.66% opined that their mode of distance / open / online course

Table-6 Students Information Seeking Behaviour for continuing Professional Development

Do you believe that information seeking behaviour enhance your CPD	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	120	100
No	0	0
Total	120	100%

This table shows that the student teachers belief of information seeking behaviour enhances continuing professional development (CPD) all the students 100% responded that information seeking behavior help and enhance their continuing professional development. The data showed that student teachers strongly believed that information seeking behaviour can empower them as student's teachers in future.

Table-7 Purpose of Information Seeking

Purpose of Information Seeking	Student Response	Percentage
Keep up with current development	43	35.83%
Academic requirements	82	68.33%
Developer competence	18	15.00%
Improve Job Competative Examination Skills	36	30.00%
Support Research	14	11.67%
Assignment/Seminar/PPTpresentation	28	23.33%
Writing Book or Article	04	3.33%
Preparation for audio/ video programmes	16	13.33%

The main purpose of the library visit is for the academic requirements which 68.33% followed by current developments 35.83% job competitive examination skills 30% ,23.33% Assignment/ Seminar/PPT presentation. The other options are not been used much by the students. This table clearly indicates the students main focus is on academics.

Table-8 Problems in seeking information

Problems in seeking information	Student Response	Percentage
Materials are not available	6	05.00%
Library staff are unwilling for service	12	10.00%
Lack of time	14	11.67%
Information materials are old	13	10.83%
Internet speed	47	39.17%
Books not arranged properly	22	18.33%
Inadequate Library staff	68	56.67%
Less no of text books etc.	24	20.00%

The above table shows the main problems faced by students in their information seeking from the library is less no. of library staff (56.67%) speed of internet in the college 39.17% and less no of the text books, etc. 20% the other problems students indicted are books not arranged properly 18.33% lack of time 11.67% information materials are old 10.83% this effects the use of e-resources in the library.

Table-9 Use of E-Resources While Seeking Information

Type of E-Resources	Student Frequency	Percentage
E-Library (Digitalized)	46	38.00%
N-LIST	40	33.00%
E-Journals	33	28.00%
E-Books	28	23.00%
Old question paper	24	20.00%
Web-page	14	12.00%

The above table shows that maximum students i.e., 46(38%) are using E-library for their information needs. While 40(33%) students are opinioned , N-LIST. Which is a good sign that students are moving towards digital content. The other e-resources . Which are used majority are ,e-journal 33(28.0%) e-books 28(23%), old question paper 24(20%) and web-page 14(12%) This table justices students are slowly but definitely moving towards digital content.

7. FINDINGS

With the study found that all B.Ed students responded that 100% they update knowledge, attitude & practice through information seeking behaviour, with focusing frequency of knowledge, attitude skills for the B.Ed programme Most of the students 77(64.17%) opined that through reading books they update their KAS & 27(22.50%) opined reading newspaper the highest no of students 79(65.83%) opinion that attending training programmes 27(22.50%) students opinion that participating in workshop/seminar PPT. etc, is their mode of seeking information. The lowest no of students 14(11.66%) opined that doing distance/open/online Course 82(68.33%) students are opinion of purpose of seeking information on Academic requirements. The most of the students are used 46(38%) opinioned through e-Library resources (Digitalize) and 40(33%) opinioned are N-LIST. The main problems faced by students in their information seeking from is less no of library staff 68(56.67%). All the students 100% responded that information seeking behaviour help & enhance their continuing professional development.

8. CONCLUSION

The main purpose of the data showed that students strongly believed that information seeking behaviour can empower then as teachers in future. On the whole, the findings show that information seeking behaviour through library& other modes highly help the students to transform themselves in updating their knowledge attitude& skills in teaching-learning process of the two year B.Ed programme Information seeking behaviour as the way people search for and utilize information seeking behaviour engage dynamic or purposeful information to complete course assignment, prepare for class discussion, seminars, PPT, workshop conferences etc. Finally to conclude majority of the students of Shri Kumareswar college of Education, Hangal, Haveri (Karnataka) in all ways information seeking behaviour can empower them as student teachers are fully highly satisfied with the library resources & services provided to them by the college library.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abels.E(2004): Information seekers perspective of Libraries & Librarians Advances in librarianship 28 Vol.PP-151-170
- [2] Case.D.O(2008) : Looking for information : A survey of research on information seeking, needs and behaviouring 3rd Ed,Bingley: Emerald Pub.Group
- [3] Dr.Keshav.R.D (2019) Information seeking behaviour of students of St. Xavier college Mapusa, Goa : A case study PP:75-85
- [4] R.Rajesh & others (2018) : Information seeking behaviour among B.Ed college students in Puduchery : A case study : International Journal Information Movement Vol,2(X):PP-110-112
- [5] Mr.Basavaraj Mali Patil & others (2020) : Information seeking behavior of students of S.U.P.F.G College Kyathasandra Tumkur (Karnataka) International Journal of Research Vol.IX (VIII) PP-227-236
- [6] Jithendra Sigh(2016) : Information Search Information searching mechanism : An overview Role of Libraries in social Empowerment Gandhi Peace Foundation, New Delhi: ISBN-978-93-80316-57-4 PP-270-75
- [7] Wilson T.D (2000) : Human information behaviour information Science 3(2) : PP-49-55